

OPPORTUNITIES TO DEVELOP CREATIVE COMPETENCIES OF SCHOOLCHILDREN IN EDUCATIONAL CLUSTER CONDITIONS

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Abstract. *An educational cluster is a set of vocational education institutions united by industry and interconnected in cooperation with industrial enterprises. The article highlights the possibilities of developing creative competences of schoolchildren in the context of an educational cluster.*

Keywords: *education cluster, production, vocational education, industry, information, school, science, training, activity.*

At a time when the process of integration and globalization in the social, economic and spiritual spheres is accelerating in the world, special attention is paid to research in the direction of strengthening the content and scientific-methodical base of training competitive personnel in accordance with international qualification requirements, and the use of innovative educational technologies. According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the state educational standards of general secondary and secondary special, vocational education" No. 187 of April 6, 2017, competence is defined as "the ability to apply existing knowledge, skills and abilities in daily activities" based on the competency-based approach " is interpreted as [1].

According to the analyzes of scientific literature and dictionaries, the word "competence" derived from the Latin word "competere" ("to be capable, worthy") means a person's awareness of a certain field, the level of knowledge in this field. From this point of view, the development of creative competences of schoolchildren in the conditions of the educational cluster acquires important scientific and practical importance. Thus, the concept of "cluster" is currently one of the most popular concepts in economics, and it is becoming more and more popular and is being used in other fields of knowledge. In addition, the analysis of specialized literature showed that there is no single approach to this concept.

For example, D. A. Yalov defines the concept of "cluster" as follows: it is a network of suppliers, producers, consumers, elements of industrial infrastructure, research institutes that are interconnected in the process of creating added value.

According to A.A. Migranyan, a cluster is a focus on the most effective and interconnected types of economic activity, that is, it provides a "golden middle" ("diamond" in the Western interpretation) in the entire economic system of the state and industrial, national and world provides competitive positions in the markets [3].

The specific characteristics of a cluster are described as follows: A cluster is a single dynamic structure; an innovation center, a stable core of new knowledge, technologies, product distribution; the cluster is interdisciplinary, has no clear boundaries, occupies a high level of

information. Based on this, the cluster is an integration mechanism, the organization of which ensures the intensive development of their social cooperation [4].

The concept of "Educational cluster" was originally related to the chain of "science-educational institution-production" and was related to ensuring the quality of general secondary, secondary special and higher professional education and creating technical, industrial, informational innovative projects and structures. In this sense, "educational cluster is a set of vocational education institutions united by fields and interconnected in cooperation with industrial enterprises" [4].

The educational cluster allows continuous "absorption" of schoolchildren in the field of future professional activity, allows them to learn, generalize and collect best practices, quickly test scientific achievements, organize professional training and update and generalize its content. In its conditions, promising specialties are opened, new sciences and modern educational technologies are introduced, and the possibility of choosing higher education systems is created. The advantages of the educational cluster are its quality, coherence, continuity, flexibility and competitiveness.

The course on sustainable development of educational clusters involves taking into account what are the main points of growth in the republic and how different interest groups can support their development. The following priority areas are distinguished in the activities of the subjects of the educational cluster under consideration:

- pre-school preparation;
- work with gifted children;
- specialized and pre-professional training;
- development of professional competences, professional development and retraining of pedagogues;
- education of children with disabilities;
- creation of a local network as a tool for the operation of a unified information-educational environment [5].

An important factor in the effectiveness of this approach is that resources are combined in cluster activities, and the common material base allows all participants of the educational process (children, parents, teachers) to use equipment, space, consulting support and other resources that are not available in their individual institution.

It should be noted that a single developing field, which includes all links and levels of education, as well as active network cooperation within it, increases the efficiency of each cluster member and allows full use of its creative potential.

Organizational and technological solutions of regulatory documents are an important condition for the proper organization of an educational cluster. Innovative changes in the modern education system and, in particular, in general secondary education have significantly changed the organization of educational work, that is, there has been a redistribution, such as a reduction of lesson hours in the educational load and, accordingly, an increase in the share of lessons at the expense of independent work of schoolchildren. In the preparation of school students, the main focus is on the independent learning process, which is impossible without the formed general competencies reflected in the educational standards. Thus, effective formation of general competencies is one of the main elements of training a qualified specialist. By efficiency, we understand a statistically significant increase in indicators describing the formation of general

competencies during the implementation of the educational process (motivational, cognitive, active, evaluation-reflexive).

The problem of formation of general competencies in general secondary educational institutions is not widely covered in pedagogical literature. Researches are dedicated to the formation of competences of students of educational institutions in the study of particular subjects or specific specialties. Professional and general competences are formed throughout the educational process. Only vocational subjects depend on specific subjects, while general competencies are not subject-specific. They are formed throughout the course. In the context of an educational cluster, schoolchildren should have the following competencies, including the "ability":

- "1. To understand the nature and social importance of the future profession, to show constant interest in it.
2. Choosing standard methods and methods for organizing one's activities, performing professional tasks, evaluating their effectiveness and quality.
3. Decision-making and responsibility for standard and non-standard situations.
4. Search for and use information necessary for effective performance of professional duties, professional and personal development.
5. Use of information and communication technologies in professional activities.
6. Working with a team, communicating effectively with colleagues, management, and consumers.
7. Taking responsibility for the work of team members (subordinates), the result of completing tasks.
8. Self-determination of professional and personal development tasks, self-education, conscious planning of professional development.
9. Adaptation to the conditions of frequent changes of technologies in professional activity".

In the conditions of the educational cluster, special importance is attached to the knowledge, abilities, skills and qualifications that determine the cognitive activity of the individual in the development of creative competences of schoolchildren. In the pedagogical dictionary, the components that make up the concept of competence are explained as follows: "knowledge is the understanding, memorization and repetition of evidence, concepts, rules, laws, theories of science", "skill is the ability to perform fully conscious actions that have not reached the highest level of formation" . By "skill" we mean the practical application of knowledge; performed at the level of automated actions by repeating (occupying) several times. The development of creative competencies of schoolchildren in the conditions of an educational cluster creates an opportunity to successfully master new knowledge, skills and competencies, including the organization of learning, that is, the ability to learn independently.

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